

Stability of mental abilities and physical growth from 6 months to 65 years: Findings from the Zurich Longitudinal Studies

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ABSTRACT

Mental abilities and physical growth are important determinants of health across the lifespan. Here, the stability of these traits was assessed from 6 months to 65 years of age to investigate periods of stability and malleability. Mental abilities, height, and weight were assessed at 11 time-points in participants of the Zurich Longitudinal Studies. Individuals with more than three missing data points per trait across the 11 assessment time-points (i.e., more than approx. 25% missing data) were excluded from further analyses (final $N = 281$). Bivariate cross-time correlations showed that the stability of mental abilities was low in infancy and gradually increased. The stability of growth measures was uniform across development, with height being highly stable and weight moderately so. When a latent model was used, the overall stability of mental abilities approached that of weight. The findings indicate that stability and malleability across development differ between mental abilities and growth measures. This requires consideration in interventions targeting these traits as facilitators for improving health outcomes.

1. Introduction

Mental abilities and physical growth such as body height and weight are important determinants of health across the lifespan. For example, lower mental abilities have been shown to increase the risk of chronic diseases (see Deary, Hill, & Gale, 2021, for an overview) and are associated with accelerated biological aging in mid-adulthood (Schaefer et al., 2016). Conversely, better early-life mental abilities have even been found to reduce all-cause mortality risk later in life (Calvin et al., 2011). Shorter height has been associated with an increased risk of coronary heart disease (Meyer et al., 2021; Paajanen, Oksala, Kuukasjarvi, & Karhunen, 2010) and metabolic disorders (Shrestha et al., 2019), whereas greater height is associated with an increased risk of various types of cancer (Abar et al., 2018; Genkinger et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2018). Moreover, retaining an optimal body weight has been shown repeatedly to benefit health in older age (Fontana & Hu, 2014). The pathways of how mental abilities and growth parameters may impact health are not yet fully understood. It has been suggested that

individuals with better mental abilities enter higher education and, thus, jobs that are saver and provide more stable financial resources, and that they adopt healthier lifestyles, including better diet, more physical activity and less smoking, altogether reducing their risk for morbidity and mortality (e.g., Deary et al., 2021). A number of plausible explanations and mechanisms have been presented that link height and health outcomes, including increased pulmonary function and coronary vessel diameter in taller people underlying their lower risk for coronary heart disease, and larger organ size and, thus, more cells at risk of malignant transformation underlying their higher risk for certain types of cancer (see Batty et al., 2009 for a comprehensive overview). Both under- and overweight are associated with alterations of the cardiovascular and the immune system, and with other health indicators, linking weight to health outcomes (e.g., Golubnitschaja et al., 2021). Further, genetic factors linked simultaneously to mental abilities, growth parameters and health have also been proposed to explain their association (Arden et al., 2015; Batty et al., 2009; Hill, Harris, & Deary, 2019). Thus, while the specific pathways linking them require further investigation, clearly,

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mental abilities and growth measures are important human traits to consider when studying health outcomes over the lifespan. In particular, the degree of their individual-order stability across development—whether individuals retain their rank within a group across time (Bornstein, Putnick, & Esposito, 2017)—may indicate potential periods of malleability, and consequently, opportunities for positive health impact. Various meta-analyses have previously provided evidence that, indeed, mental abilities and growth parameters may be influenced by interventions. For example, working memory training (e.g., Au et al., 2015), learning a musical instrument (e.g., Protzko, 2017) and, physical exercise interventions (Ludyga, Gerber, Pühse, Looser, & Kamijo, 2020) have been reported to improve mental abilities. Further, multi-component behavior changing interventions were found to reduce weight and continued weight gain in overweighted children and adolescents (e.g., Ells et al., 2018; Sneathen, Broome, Treisman, Castro, & Kelber, 2016; Whitlock, O'Connor, Williams, Beil, & Lutz, 2010) and in the general population (e.g., Luckner, Moss, & Gericke, 2011; Peirson et al., 2015), and counselling about nutrition was found to reduce stunting and related burden of disease (e.g., Bhutta et al., 2008). For the optimal effectiveness of interventions that target mental abilities, height, and weight as facilitators of health improvement, a better understanding of their patterns of stability and malleability across the lifespan is needed.

Numerous studies have previously investigated this. For mental abilities, it has generally been established that stability increases with age and decreases at longer time-lags between assessments (Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014). More specifically, stability of mental abilities has been reported to be low in infancy, to increase in early childhood and to be reasonably high after mid-childhood and across adulthood (Bayley, 1949; Beam et al., 2020; Hertzog & Schaie, 1986; Honzik, Macfarlane, & Allen, 1948; Jenni et al., 2011; Larsen, Hartmann, & Nyborg, 2008; Moffitt, Caspi, Harkness, & Silva, 1993; Perret & Fischer, 1971; Rönnlund, Sundström, & Nilsson, 2015; Schneider, Niklas, & Schmiedeler, 2014; Terman & Oden, 1959; Wilson, 1983; Yu, McCoach, Gottfried, & Gottfried, 2018). Findings from the Lothian Birth Cohort, to date the study with the longest time-span between assessments, indicate that one third of the variability of mental abilities at 90 years of age may be accounted for by mental abilities at 11 years of age (Deary, Pattie, & Starr, 2013). Height has been found to be highly stable from infancy onwards (Jenni et al., 2011; Jenni, Molinari, Caflich, & Largo, 2007; Rarick & Smoll, 1967; Sheehy, Gasser, Largo, & Molinari, 2002; Tanner, 1962), with studies even reporting length at birth to be positively associated with later height across childhood and adulthood (Eide et al., 2005; Jelenkovic et al., 2018; Karlberg & Luo, 2000). Finally, weight has been shown to be moderately stable from infancy to adulthood (Jenni et al., 2007; Rarick & Smoll, 1967).

Studies on trait stability vary substantially in the age of individuals at the time of assessments, the lags between assessment time-points (ranging from months to decades), the sample composition (population sample vs. selected group of individuals), and the analytic methods used to quantify stability (e.g., cross-time correlations vs. latent model approaches). This impedes the comparison of stability patterns across different domains. However, comparing the stability patterns of various traits may advance the understanding of how these traits develop and provide insights into the timing and the degree of environmental and genetic contributions across developmental periods. In fact, the stronger influence of exogenous factors, including nutritional behavior and physical activity, on weight than on other growth measures such as sitting and standing height has been suggested to underlie the lower stability of weight than height between one month and twenty years of age (Sheehy et al., 2002). Further, while a substantial part of mental abilities may be explained by genetics (e.g., Plomin & von Stumm, 2018), early childhood socio-economic status (SES) has also been shown to be strongly linked to mental abilities at other developmental periods (e.g., Cermakova, Formanek, Kagstrom, & Winkler, 2018; Tucker-Drob, 2013), and a meta-analysis found persistent positive effects of additional

years of education on mental abilities across the lifespan (Ritchie & Tucker-Drob, 2018). Generally, the heritability of growth has been reported to be higher than that of mental abilities (Polderman et al., 2015), and the relative environmental and genetic contribution to their stability was found to differ considerably between these traits across development, with an earlier shift from a major contribution of the environment to that of genetics in growth compared to mental abilities (Dubois et al., 2012; Johnson, 2010; Silventoinen et al., 2008; Silventoinen, Posthuma, van Beijsterveldt, Bartels, & Boomsma, 2006; Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014).

The aim of the current study was to concurrently investigate the stability of mental abilities, height, and weight from infancy (i.e., 6 months of age) to mid-to-older adulthood (i.e., 65 years of age) in the same cohort, namely, in participants of the Zurich Longitudinal Studies (Wehrle et al., 2021). Due to the different degrees of the genetic and the environmental contribution to the various traits across development, it is hypothesized that height is the most stable of the three, and that the timing of the greatest stability differs between the three traits.

2. Method

2.1. Participants and study procedure

The data originates from the Zurich Longitudinal Studies (ZLS), a set of three longitudinal cohort studies initiated in the 1950s (first cohort) and the 1970s (second and third cohorts). The original aim of the ZLS was to describe health and development from birth to young adulthood (approximately 18 years of age). Since 2019, the studies have been further expanded (Wehrle et al., 2021). For the current analyses, data assessed in the first ZLS cohort was considered because this cohort spans the longest period of the three ZLS cohorts: from infancy to mid-to-older adulthood.

Between 1954 and 1961, 432² infants born into Swiss families in Zurich, Switzerland, were enrolled at birth and subsequently assessed >20 times across infancy, childhood, adolescence, and into young adulthood. The most recent assessment took place in mid-to-older adulthood when participants were at a mean age of 65 years. At every assessment, detailed information on the physical, motor, and mental development of the participants was collected through standardized instruments, and through (semi-)structured interviews and questionnaires completed by the parents or the participants themselves (see Wehrle et al., 2021, for details on the full study protocol). At 11 assessment time-points, namely, at 6, 9, 12, and 18 months, at 2, 3, 5, 8, 11, and 14 years, and at the most recent visit at the age of 65 years, mental abilities and growth measures were assessed concurrently. Thus, these time-points were considered for all further analyses. Fig. 1 depicts the detailed flowchart.

2.2. Assessment instruments

Every assessment from infancy to young adulthood was conducted by a psychologist or a developmental pediatrician and by a psychologist or trained psychology student at the most recent visit at age 65 years. All assessments were performed at the University Children's Hospital Zurich, Switzerland. The assessment instruments in childhood were selected to match those of several other European studies on child development. The International Children's Center (ICC), an institution founded in 1950 by the French government and UNICEF, had initiated this set of harmonized longitudinal studies and the first ZLS-cohort was one of them (Wehrle et al., 2021).

Mental Abilities. Mental abilities were assessed with a range of age-

² This number differs from that published in Wehrle et al., 2021 ($N = 445$) because subsequent investigations revealed that 13 participants had incorrectly been listed as enrolled at birth. No data had been assessed in these individuals.

Fig. 1. Flow chart.

^a See Wehrle et al., (2021) for details.

^b Data from infancy to young adulthood are available in these individuals and may be used for analyses (see Wehrle et al., 2021, for details on ethical considerations).

appropriate standardized tests at each of the 11 assessments. Generally, the term “mental abilities” refers to the performance measured by tests that determine spatial awareness, perceptual speed, number sense, vocabulary, memory, inductive reasoning, and so forth (American Psychological Association, 2022). In infancy, preliminary stages of mental abilities may be determined with developmental tests (e.g., Bornstein et al., 2006), and intelligence tests are used from childhood onwards. Throughout this paper, the term mental abilities is used to describe indicators of mental development, assessed with either a developmental test in infancy or with conceptually related age-appropriate intelligence tests subsequently.

In infancy (i.e., at 6, 9, 12 and 18 months, and at 2 years), the Brunet-Lézine Scale of Psychomotor Development of Children (BL), a French adaptation of the Gesell Developmental Scales (Gesell, 1925; Gesell &

Amatruda, 1947; Hoben, 1970), was conducted (Brunet & Lézine, 1951). The BL contains four subscales: gross motor skills, fine motor skills, language skills and social skills (see Supplementary Table S1 for exemplary items). The four subscales are combined into an age-normed composite score. The BL composite score has a mean of 100, and 50% of the values are between 90 and 110 (Brunet & Lézine, 1951). The manual of the original version of the BL does not provide information on reliability. An informative approximation may, however, be derived from the revised version of the BL ($r = 0.85$ after one month, Brunet & Lézine, 1965). At preschool age (i.e., at 3 and 5 years) and in childhood (i.e., at 8 and 11 years), the Stanford-Binet Test of Intelligence (SB; L form at 3 years, M form at 5, 8, and 11 years) was used (Lückert, 1957; Terman & Merrill, 1937). The SB provides a single, age-normed score. For the SB score, a mean of 100 is reported with a standard deviation of 17 (Terman

& Merrill, 1937). Parallel-form reliability between forms M and L administered within a few days was reported as 0.88 for two- to six-year-olds and 0.93 for children older than six years (Terman & Merrill, 1937). Test-retest reliability is not specified in the manual but was found to be 0.80 after six months and 0.94 after one year in 2.5- and 7.5-year-old children (Black, 1939). In adolescence (i.e., at 14 years), the AH4 Group Test of General Intelligence (AH4) was conducted (Heim, 1970). The AH4 consists of a verbal-numerical and a perceptual part, which are combined into a composite score. For the AH4 composite score, a mean of 85 and a standard deviation of 11, and a mean of 60 and a standard deviation of 20 is described for two different populations of 14-year-old secondary school children (Heim, 1970). Retest reliability after one month was reported to be 0.92 (Heim, 1970). At the most recent visit in mid-to-older adulthood (i.e., at mean age 65 years), a comprehensive test battery was used to assess mental abilities (described in detail in Wehrle et al., 2021). Among others, this included six subtests of the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale IV, German version (WAIS-IV, Petermann & Petermann, 2012): Similarities, Digit Span, Block Design, Matrix Reasoning, Symbol Search, and Coding. Internal consistency of these subtests ranges from 0.84 to 0.91 (Petermann & Petermann, 2012). To obtain a composite score, the raw scores of each of these subtests were z-transformed using the mean and standard deviation of all participants included in the current analysis, and all subtests were then averaged. For a more comparable scale with the other tests of mental abilities, the composite scores were transformed to an IQ-scale (i.e., multiplied by 15 and 100 added).

Growth Measures. Height was measured in the supine position in all children until 9 months of age. From 3 years onward, height was measured in the standing position with a stadiometer in all children. At the 12 and 18 months, and the 2 year assessment, children were measured either in the supine or in the standing position. The measurements were read to the nearest millimeter. In infants, weight was measured in the weighing pan. At later assessments, children stood on a beam balance with an accuracy of 0.1 kg (for a more detailed description of the assessment of growth measures, see Prader, Largo, Molinari, & Issler, 1989).

Childhood Socioeconomic Status (SES). Information on the level of parental occupation and education was collected with standardized scales at various time-points in childhood. For the current analyses, the earliest available time-point per child was used, ranging from 1 month to 5 years of age. To estimate childhood SES, the information was transformed into a five-point scale for paternal occupation and maternal education, and these indicators were subsequently combined into a single score ranging from 2 to 10, following Largo et al. (1986). Higher scores indicate lower SES. If either of the indicators was missing, the available indicator was doubled. If neither of the indicators was available but either paternal education or maternal occupation was available instead, this information was used to estimate childhood SES. Finally, SES scores were grouped into three social classes of comparable group sizes (2–5 = high; 6 = medium; 7–10 = low).

2.3. Statistical analyses

Individuals with more than three missing data points per trait across the 11 assessment time-points (i.e., more than approx. 25% missing data) were excluded from further analyses ($n = 128$). All analyses were performed using R Statistical Software (v4.2.1; R Core Team, 2022).

Sample characteristics, mental abilities, and growth measures at each time-point are reported as proportions or means (95% confidence interval [CI]). For individuals with <25% missing data, incomplete variables were imputed under fully conditional specification, using the default settings of the ‘multivariate imputation by chained equation (MICE)’ package in R (v3.14; Van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). The percentage of missing values for the variables ranged from 0 to 53%. In total, 230 of 281 participants (82%) had an incomplete data set. According to a rule of thumb, the number of imputations should

correspond to the percentage of incomplete cases (Bodner, 2008; White, Royston, & Wood, 2011). Accordingly, 82 imputed datasets with 20 iterations were created, based on the available data at each of the 11 time-points, and on sex and childhood SES. All further analyses were performed on the 82 imputed datasets and Rubin’s rules were applied to obtain overall estimates.

First, Pearson correlations (for mental abilities) and Pearson partial correlations (for height and weight, controlling for sex) were used to test bivariate cross-time correlations across the 11 assessment time-points using the ‘miceadds’ package in R (v3.13–12; Robitzsch & Grund, 2022). Correlation coefficients were interpreted as stability coefficients according to Cohen (1988), with $r \geq 0.50$ indicating large effects, $r \geq 0.30$ indicating medium effects, $r \geq 0.10$ indicating small effects, and $r < 0.10$ indicating negligible effects. Bivariate cross-time correlations have been described as well-suited for the analysis of *homotypic* stability: the stability of the same characteristic measured in the same metric over time (Bornstein et al., 2017). The stability of growth measures such as height and weight likely qualifies as an example of homotypic stability. In contrast, the stability of many psychological constructs, including mental abilities, is described as *heterotypic* (Bornstein et al., 2017): The characteristics assessed over time are different, for instance because different age-appropriate tests are required at different developmental periods, but the characteristics are presumed to share the same underlying construct, such as mental abilities. Latent variables have the capacity to account for the variance introduced by differences in the measurements at various time-points; consequently, it has been suggested that latent models are more suitable for estimating heterotypic stability than are bivariate cross-time correlations (Bornstein et al., 2017).

Thus, the stability of mental abilities was further examined with a latent variable model. The confirmatory factor analysis approach (CFA) implemented in ‘lavaan’ (v0.6–11; Rosseel, 2012), an R package for structural equation modeling supported by the package ‘semTools’ (v0.5–6; Jorgensen, Pornprasertmanit, Schoemann, & Rosseel, 2022) was used. Based on the 11 available assessment time-points, the factors of the model were defined to represent five developmental periods: infancy (6 months–2 years), preschool age (3–5 years), childhood (8–11 years), adolescence (14 years), and mid-to-older adulthood (65 years). For infancy, preschool age, and childhood, the test scores of each developmental period were used as manifest indicators to model the latent variables; for instance, for preschool age, the test scores were assessed at ages 3 and 5 years. In adolescence and adulthood, mental abilities were assessed at only one time-point. Consequently, no latent variables could be modelled at these time-points. Instead, these test scores were included in the model as manifest variables. For simplicity, the five variables representing the five developmental periods are all termed ‘factors’: the three latent variables for infancy, preschool age, and childhood and the two manifest variables assessed in adolescence and adulthood. The five factors in the model were allowed to covary. Further, covariances between test scores of adjacent infancy assessments were accounted for as this improved the model fit.

To assess the fit of the models, comparative fit index (CFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) and its 90% CI, and standardized root mean square residuals (SRMR) were considered. CFI values above 0.95, RMSEA values below 0.05, and SRMR values below 0.05 are assumed to reflect a good fit, and CFI values above 0.90, RMSEA values below 0.08, and SRMR values below 0.10 are acceptable (Gäde, Schermelleh-Engel, & Brandt, 2020).

The covariance between the factors of the model, representing the five development periods, was interpreted as rank-order stability coefficients according to Cohen (1988), and thus, they were used to assess the stability of mental abilities over time.

Further, three sensitivity analyses were calculated: First, the analyses were repeated without imputation of missing data, i.e., with available data only (n between 108 and 275 at the different assessment time-points) to further assess the robustness of the results. Second, only

those participants with complete data across all 11 assessment time-points were considered to check whether the stability coefficients of the bivariate cross-time correlations remain similar when only complete cases are included ($n = 51$). Third, 25 families included more than one child in the study; consequently, the potential influence of kinship on the stability coefficients was tested. To do this, a subsample was created for which one child per family was randomly selected and included in the analyses ($n = 256$).

2.4. Ethics

The study was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich, Switzerland (Basec-Nr. 2018-00686). Details on the informed consent procedure since the initiation of the study in 1954 are provided in Wehrle et al., (2021).

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics and descriptive statistics

Of the 409 participants for whom data were initially available (Fig. 1), only those were included with three or fewer missing data points per trait across the 11 assessments from 6 months to age 65 years (i.e., less than approx. 25% missing data, $N = 281$). Of the 281 participants, 53% ($n = 148$) were male. Childhood SES was low, medium, and high in 34% ($n = 96$), 38% ($n = 106$), and 28% ($n = 79$), respectively. From infancy to young adulthood, study visits were scheduled ± 14 days around the child’s birthday for the 6- to 18-month visits and ± 30 days around the child’s birthday after that. Hence, all children were of comparable age at the time of the assessments. At the most recent assessment in mid-to-older adulthood, participants were between 61.22 and 67.49 years old ($M = 65.10$ years, 95% CI [64.94, 65.27]). Descriptive statistics of mental abilities and growth measures at each of the 11 assessment time-points are shown in Supplementary Table S2a, S2b, and S2c.

A set of three analyses investigated a potential drop-out bias as has previously been shown to occur in longitudinal studies (e.g., Gustavson, von Soest, Karevold, & Roysamb, 2012). The findings indicate that

individuals who were included in the analyses, i.e., those with <25% missing data ($n = 281$), those who had participated in the most recent assessment in mid-to-older adulthood ($n = 154$) and those who had participated in all 11 assessment time-points (complete cases, $n = 51$), generally, had higher family SES and better mental abilities compared to those who were excluded (i.e., those with >25% missing data, $n = 128$), those who had not participated in the most recent assessment in mid-to-older adulthood ($n = 255$), and those with incomplete data ($n = 358$; Supplementary Tables S2a to S4c for details).

3.2. Bivariate Cross-Time Correlations to Assess Stability of Mental Abilities and Growth Measures

Table 1a shows the stability coefficients of mental abilities across the 11 assessment time-points. They were medium to large within the infancy developmental period, and large within the preschool, and childhood developmental periods. Table 1b shows the stability coefficients of height and weight across the 11 assessment time-points. For height, they were large, and for weight, they were small to large across all assessment time-points. Supplementary Figs. S1 to S3 illustrate the stability patterns of the three traits across development. The stability pattern of weight remained very similar when height was taken into account (Supplementary Fig. S4).

Results remained similar if the analyses were repeated without imputation of missing data and if only one randomly selected child per family was included. Stability coefficients were slightly higher in the complete case analyses (Supplementary Table S5a-S7b).

Fig. 2 shows the stability coefficients between the assessments across infancy, childhood, and adolescence, and the most recent assessment at age 65 years. For mental abilities, stability coefficients with age-65 mental abilities increased from negligible-to-small in infancy to large in childhood and adolescence. Stability coefficients with age-65 growth measures were large from infancy to adolescence for height and small-to-medium for weight.

3.3. Five-factor latent model to assess stability of mental abilities

The five-factor latent model showed an acceptable fit, with CFI =

Table 1a
Bivariate cross-time correlations of mental abilities across eleven assessments from infancy to mid-to-older adulthood.

Test	Age	6 M	9 M	12 M	18 M	2 Y	3 Y	5 Y	8 Y	11 Y	14 Y	
BL	6 M	-										
BL	9 M	.56***	-									$r \geq .50$ large effect
BL	12 M	.58***	.59***	-								$r \geq .30$ medium effect
BL	18 M	.48***	.47***	.51***	-							$r \geq .10$ small effect
BL	2 Y	.32***	.32***	.35***	.63***	-						$r < .10$ negligible effect
SB-L	3 Y	.20**	.19**	.18**	.33***	.44***	-					
SB-M	5 Y	.15*	.08	.10	.31***	.33***	.56***	-				
SB-M	8 Y	.07	.06	.09	.25***	.30***	.55***	.63***	-			
SB-M	11 Y	.06	-.02	.02	.22***	.25***	.46***	.46***	.69***	-		
AH4	14 Y	.08	-.02	.07	.15*	.22**	.35***	.48***	.62***	.60***	-	
WAIS	65 Y	.14	.12	.22**	.17	.36***	.41***	.40***	.49***	.50***	.58***	

Note. Pearson correlation. The background color represents the strength of the effect size according to Cohen (1988). $N = 281$ (imputed dataset). M = months; Y = years; AH4 = AH4 Group Test of General Intelligence (Heim, 1970); BL = Brunet-Lézine Scale of Psychomotor Development of Children, (Brunet & Lézine, 1951); SB-L/SB-M = Stanford-Binet Test of Intelligence L-Form/M-Form (Lückert, 1957; Terman & Merrill, 1937); WAIS = composite score of six selected WAIS-IV subtests (Petermann & Petermann, 2012).

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 1b

Bivariate cross-time correlations of height (lower triangle) and weight (upper triangle) across 11 assessments from infancy to mid-to-older adulthood.

Age	6 M	9 M	12 M	18 M	2 Y	3 Y	5 Y	8 Y	11 Y	14 Y	65Y
6 M	-	.85***	.75***	.65***	.60***	.56***	.49***	.41***	.38***	.33***	.22*
9 M	.87***	-	.92***	.80***	.74***	.69***	.61***	.51***	.46***	.41***	.25**
12 M	.84***	.89***	-	.88***	.82***	.77***	.67***	.56***	.48***	.41***	.30***
18 M	.78***	.82***	.88***	-	.93***	.88***	.78***	.64***	.51***	.44***	.35***
2 Y	.76***	.81***	.86***	.91***	-	.94***	.85***	.69***	.57***	.48***	.35***
3 Y	.70***	.76***	.81***	.88***	.94***	-	.90***	.77***	.62***	.52***	.30***
5 Y	.69***	.74***	.78***	.86***	.91***	.95***	-	.90***	.76***	.66***	.30***
8 Y	.65***	.71***	.73***	.80***	.86***	.90***	.96***	-	.89***	.79***	.34***
11 Y	.60***	.67***	.68***	.74***	.80***	.83***	.90***	.96***	-	.86***	.33***
14 Y	.55***	.62***	.62***	.66***	.73***	.72***	.78***	.85***	.87***	-	.34***
65 Y	.61***	.61***	.60***	.64***	.69***	.69***	.70***	.75***	.70***	.68***	-

Note. Pearson partial correlation controlled for sex. The background color represents the strength of the effect size according to Cohen (1988). N = 281 (imputed dataset). M = months; Y = years.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Fig. 2. Stability of mental abilities, height, and weight between the assessments in infancy, childhood, and adolescence and the assessment in mid-to-older adulthood (at a mean age of 65 years). Pearson correlation for mental abilities and Pearson partial correlation (controlled for sex) for growth measures. The whiskers correspond to the 95% confidence intervals (CIs) of the stability coefficients. N = 281 (imputed dataset). M = months; Y = years.

0.96, RMSEA [90% CI] = 0.064 [0.042, 0.086], and SRMR = 0.087. The standardized factor loadings of the model were all above 0.50 (Supplementary Table S8), indicating that the test scores are predicted by the corresponding latent factors (Brown, 2015). Fig. 3 illustrates the rank-order stability coefficients of the model. They ranged from small between infancy and adolescence to large between preschool age and childhood. Rank-order stability coefficients were large between preschool, childhood, and adolescence and mid-to-older adulthood, whereas they were small between infancy and mid-to-older adulthood.

Compared to the stability coefficients of the Pearson correlation, the stability coefficients of the latent model were generally higher. For example, between preschool age and mid-to-older adulthood, stability increased from 0.41 (at 3 years) and 0.40 (at 5 years) to 0.54 in the latent model. Between childhood and mid-to-older adulthood, stability

increased from 0.49 (at 8 years) and 0.50 (at 11 years) to 0.59. Fig. 4 (left boxplot) illustrates this: It displays stability coefficients of mental abilities across the 11 assessments from infancy into mid-to-older adulthood estimated with bivariate cross-time correlations compared to stability coefficients estimated with the latent model approach across five developmental periods. The median was higher when using a latent model approach than with bivariate correlation (red line, left boxplot Fig. 4). Median mental ability stability as estimated with a latent model remained below the median stability coefficients of height (middle boxplot) but was comparable to the median stability of weight (right boxplot).

Fig. 3. Five-factor latent model of mental abilities with covariances between adjacent assessments in infancy. Rectangles represent manifest variables, and ovals represent latent variables. One-headed arrows represent regressions or loadings, curved double-headed arrows represent covariances. Coefficients above the curved double-headed arrows indicate rank-order stability coefficients. The factor loadings and the coefficients of the covariances in infancy are not shown. $N = 281$ (imputed dataset). M = months; Y = years; AH4 = AH4 Group Test of General Intelligence (Heim, 1970); BL = Brunet-Lézine Scale of Psychomotor Development of Children (Brunet & Lézine, 1951); SB-L/SB-M = Stanford-Binet Test of Intelligence L-Form/M-Form (Luckert, 1957; Terman & Merrill, 1937); WAIS = composite score of six selected WAIS-IV subtests (Petermann & Petermann, 2012).

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Fig. 4. Stability coefficients across 11 assessments from infancy into mid-to-older adulthood. In blue: stability coefficients from cross-time correlations with boxplot. In red: stability coefficients from latent model with median line. $N = 281$ (imputed dataset). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4. Discussion

The current study investigated the stability patterns of three human traits known to affect health across the lifespan: mental abilities, height, and weight. The stability of height was high within and between developmental periods and showed very little change from 6 months to 65 years of age. Weight mirrored this uniform pattern across time, with

the coefficients being substantially lower than those of height, even after height was taken into account. Bivariate cross-time correlations revealed that stability of mental abilities was low in infancy and increased across development to reach a high level by childhood and adolescence. Once measurement errors across different assessment time-points were accounted for with a latent modeling approach, the overall level of stability of mental abilities became comparable to that of weight, with stability of mental abilities remaining high from preschool age onward while that of weight was moderate across all time-points.

The overall greater stability of growth measures, in particular of height, compared to mental abilities is in line with previous studies investigating stability patterns separately in these traits (Jenni et al., 2007; Rarick & Smoll, 1967; Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014). The strong genetic control of human growth (Lettre, 2011) likely underlies the impressive phenotypic stability of growth measures across various developmental periods, as has previously been shown for height from birth into young adulthood (Silventoinen et al., 2008). Twin studies have provided evidence that the heritability of growth is considerably higher than that of mental abilities (Polderman et al., 2015), supporting the notion that differences in the genetic contribution to these traits may contribute to their different overall stability levels.

The current study is the first to directly compare the stability patterns of mental abilities, height, and weight within the same cohort of individuals from infancy to mid-to-older adulthood. The difference in the stability patterns of these traits across development is striking: the stability of height and weight is characterized by a pronounced uniformity from infancy into mid-to-older adulthood, whereas the stability of mental abilities increases gradually across development. Interestingly, the environmental contribution to the stability of mental abilities has previously been shown to decrease gradually across childhood and adolescence while the genetic contribution increases (Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014). This aligns well with the pattern of increasing phenotypic stability of mental abilities across development observed in the current study. The shift from a major contribution of the environment to that of genetics has been shown to occur earlier in growth measures than it does in mental abilities, with some studies reporting an exponential increase of the genetic contribution within the first years of life (Dubois et al., 2012; Johnson, 2010; Silventoinen et al., 2006; Silventoinen et al., 2008). Again, this fits well with the high level of stability, particularly for height, from very early in life onwards that was observed in the current study. The difference in the relative genetic and environmental contribution to the stability of mental abilities and growth parameters

across development may, thus, contribute to the differential stability pattern of these traits.

Previously, the concept of gene-environment correlation has been suggested to provide a framework for explaining the increasing stability of traits across development (Briley & Tucker-Drob, 2017; Sauce & Matzel, 2018; Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014). Gene-environment correlation describes the observation that “individuals with particular genotypes for a trait are more likely to experience particular environments” (Sauce & Matzel, 2018, p. 28). Individuals have frequently been observed to select their environments in alignment with their mental abilities (termed “active covariance”; see e.g., Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014, for details and for other types of gene-environment correlations). Individuals’ opportunities for self-initiated selection of their environments may be limited in infancy and preschool age, when children spend much time with their parents or in small groups that have been selected for them, such as day care. However, these opportunities arise more frequently as they grow older, enter school, and build independent social relations with peers. The growing gene-environment correlation may then lead to a gradual increase in the phenotypical stability of mental abilities across childhood and adolescence that is apparent in the current study and has been shown by many others (see Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014, for a meta-analysis). Similarly, during the first year of life, the feeding of infants is largely regulated by the caregivers, but children increasingly choose and regulate their food intake as they grow older, with their genetic predisposition impacting their selection (Birch & Fisher, 1998). However, the active selection of the environment for feeding starts much earlier than it does for mental abilities, during the transition from a milk diet to an omnivorous diet in infancy and early childhood. Accordingly, the current findings indicate that the slight trend of increasing stability in height and weight ceases at approximately 12 months of age and is followed by a pattern of uniform stability thereafter. This likely indicates the start of the increasingly self-initiated selection of the environment and the establishment of gene-environment correlations early in life. Importantly, this pattern may change under adverse conditions: for example, catch-up growth has been described after prolonged periods of malnutrition (e.g., Jee, Baron, Phillip, & Bhutta, 2014). Whether the increasing proportion of individuals suffering from adiposity impacts the patterns of stability and malleability in growth measures across the lifespan remains to be investigated. However, gene-environment correlation has not only been shown in mental abilities and growth but has been used to explain the unique stability patterns of other human traits, including the prolonged period of increasing stability in personality (Briley & Tucker-Drob, 2017).

Besides comparing the stability patterns of different traits, the current study also used a latent model approach to estimate the heterotypic stability of mental abilities (Bornstein et al., 2017). This increased the level of stability compared to the bivariate cross-time correlation analyses, in line with a previous study on the stability of mental abilities from infancy into adolescence (Yu, McCoach, et al., 2018). The current findings expand the latter by providing evidence of small to medium level stability of mental abilities from infancy into mid-to-older adulthood—a time-span of more than six decades. Even more remarkable, at preschool age, stability into mid-to-older adulthood was high ($r = 0.54$), even exceeding previous reports of test score correlations between preschool age and young adulthood ($r = 0.46$; Schneider et al., 2014). The high stability level of mental abilities from childhood onward and into mid-to-older adulthood was generally comparable to previous results of other long-term longitudinal studies and meta-analytic reports (see Conley, 1984; Deary, 2014; Tucker-Drob & Briley, 2014). The current study provides evidence that a latent model may be particularly appropriate when estimating the stability of mental abilities from early life onwards as this approach may account for some of the challenges associated with testing young children (see Strengths and Limitations section for details on this).

When using a latent model, the stability of mental abilities became comparable to that of weight, with both of these traits being less stable

compared to height. This indicates that mental abilities and weight are more malleable than height overall and may, thus, be more promising interventional targets to improve health. More importantly however, the findings of the current study provide clear evidence that interventions targeting mental abilities and growth parameters as facilitators to improve health should consider the differential stability patterns of these traits across development. For one, the uniform stability pattern of growth parameters from early life onwards identified no unique period of opportunity for positive health impact. Arguably, for height, interventions are challenging altogether due to its high level of stability, likely, with the exception of unusual conditions, such as catch-up growth after malnutrition in infancy and early childhood (e.g., Jee et al., 2014). As the stability (and more importantly, the malleability) of weight is similar across different developmental periods, interventions may be effective at different ages. This interpretation is in line with findings that showed similar effectiveness of weight management interventions in children and in adults (Luckner et al., 2011). As childhood overweight and obesity are important risk factors for adult obesity (e.g., Simmonds, Llewellyn, Owen, & Woolacott, 2016), interventions that target weight in early life may be sensible nonetheless. However, interventions at later ages may still be beneficial. This is of importance, as the majority of obese adults were of normal weight as children (Simmonds et al., 2016). Finally, the increasing stability (and more importantly, the decreasing malleability) of mental abilities across development clearly suggests that interventions aimed at improving mental abilities should be implemented in early life for maximal effectiveness. While numerous studies have shown that interventions in the elderly do have the capacity to improve mental abilities (e.g., Kelly et al., 2014; Nguyen, Murphy, & Andrews, 2019; Vaportzis, Niechcial, & Gow, 2019), this interpretation is in line with studies that identified early mental abilities as an important predictor of adult outcome, including morbidity and mortality (e.g., Calvin et al., 2017; Schaefer et al., 2016; Wrulich et al., 2014). Early interventions to improve mental abilities may, thus, have the potential to improve outcome in subsequent developmental periods. Ultimately, studies are needed that systematically assess the impact of interventions targeting mental abilities and growth parameters as facilitators of health improvement and their differential effectiveness associated with the timing of implementation.

5. Strengths and limitations

The strengths of the current study include the repeated assessments of mental abilities and growth measures from 6 months to 65 years of age in the same individuals. This allowed the investigation and comparison of stability patterns across a large proportion of the lifespan in these important traits. By using a latent model, the current study revealed for the first time that the stability of mental abilities is substantial from preschool age until mid-to-older adulthood. In fact, by recognizing the stability of mental abilities as heterotypic, the current study accounted for several limitations that are inherent to assessing mental abilities across developmental periods and that, consequently, also apply to the current study. Chief among these is that mental abilities were assessed in different ways at different time-points across development, with developmental tests used in early childhood and formal intelligence tests at later time-points. Young children are not yet able to express their thoughts verbally but often express them through motor actions. Consequently, the level of motor development more strongly affects the assessment of mental abilities in infancy than at later time-points. Further, the reliability of mental ability tests used at younger ages may be lower compared to that of tests used at older ages, partly due to more variable day-to-day performance in younger children than older ones. All of these factors impact the stability estimates of mental abilities while this is not the case for growth measures. A latent model can account for some of these factors and thus estimates stability of mental abilities from early life onwards more accurately. Nonetheless, a considerable amount of variance in mental abilities remains

unaccounted for and future efforts should approach this. For example, understanding how the cognitive profile that defines overall mental abilities evolves differently between individuals across development may provide additional insight into the stability pattern of mental abilities from infancy into adulthood.

A specific limitation of the current study is the data gap between adolescence (14 years) and mid-to-older adulthood (65 years). The stability patterns of mental abilities and growth measures during this time interval can only be extrapolated from the available data, but the current study cannot provide information about the dynamics of stability during this time.

The sample size of the current study is limited, with many individuals not having attended at every assessment. Importantly, those who provided more data, i.e., those who remained longer in the study across childhood and adolescence, those who participated in mid-to-older adulthood, and those who missed few intermediate assessments, generally, came from higher socio-economic backgrounds and had better mental abilities compared to those who provided less data, i.e., those who had dropped-out of the study across time or who had frequently missed intermediate assessments. They neither differed with regard to sex distribution nor height or weight. Thus, the well-described systematic drop-out bias that affects many longitudinal studies (e.g., Gustavson et al., 2012) also affects the ZLS. Using multiple imputation based on all available data, and on sex and SES to account for missing data likely reduced the risk of biased estimates, as has previously been shown (Gustavson et al., 2012). Nonetheless, the systematic loss of participants across time needs to be considered when interpreting the findings.

6. Conclusion and outlook

The findings of the current study provide evidence that the patterns of stability and malleability from infancy into mid-to-older adulthood differ between mental abilities and growth measures. As these traits are known to impact health across the lifespan, this requires consideration when planning any interventions that target mental abilities, height, or weight as facilitators to improve health outcomes. Further long-term longitudinal studies will be essential to the endeavor to better understand the factors that affect human health across the lifespan.

Open practices statement

A detailed protocol of the Zurich Longitudinal Studies has been published previously (Wehrle et al., 2021). Neither the data assessment nor the analyses reported in this article were formally preregistered. Neither the data nor the materials have been made available on a permanent third-party archive due to ethical regulations; requests for the data or materials can be sent via email to the lead author at flavia.wehrle@kispi.uzh.ch.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dominique A. Eichelberger: Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration. **Fabio Sticca:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Dinah R. Kübler:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Tanja H. Kakebeke:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jon A. Cafilisch:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Oskar G. Jenni:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Flavia M. Wehrle:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2023.101730>.

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